

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

MONITORING MISSIONS OF THE UNPO (UNREPRESENTED NATIONS AND PEOPLE ORGANIZATION) IN ABKHAZIA IN 1992-1993S

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Abstract

The Unrepresented Nations and Peoples Organization (UNPO) began to take shape in the late 1980s. Among its founding members were individuals persecuted by communist regimes, such as the leader of the Estonian Congress and sinologist Linnart Mäll, the Uyghur representative Erkin Alptekin, and Lodi Gyari from Tibet. The organization was led by Dutch law professor Michael van Walt van Praag, who also served as an advisor to the 14th Dalai Lama.

The UNPO was officially established in February 1991 at the Peace Palace in The Hague. Among its founding members was the Republic of Georgia, which held full membership status from 11 February 1991 until 31 July 1992, when it became a member of the United Nations—accession to which is the main reason for the termination of Georgia's UNPO membership. Nevertheless, for a certain period, Georgia maintained the status of a “supporting member.” In 1992, the Abkhaz side also joined the organization, which subsequently prepared three biased and anti-Georgian reports concerning the Abkhazian War. This paper will examine each of these reports in detail.

Keywords: UNPO, International Organization, War in Abkhazia.

Preamble

As a result of the events developed in Tbilisi in December, 1991, and January, 1992, the legal government was overthrown, and a so called “Military Council” came to power. In fact, civil war was still going in the country. The stated process, in its turn, was followed by a particular activation of Abkhazian separatists, which “was generally expressed in legal disorders carried with rude violation of the Constitution of Georgia and solely Abkhazia and full ignorance of the Regulation of the Superior Council of Abkhazia”.

On the 9th of May of 1992, “National Union Council” was founded which was protecting interests of the Georgian side in Abkhazia and carried negotiations with a moderate part of separatists. On the 19th of May the first Georgian Division, - Sokhumi’s Mechanized Battalion was formed. On the 23rd of July, separatistic part of the Superior Council of Abkhazia, with vivid procedural violations and illegally, in contradiction with the will of Georgian MPs, adopted a Decree and restored the so called “Constitution of the Abkhazian Soviet Socialistic Republic of 1925”. The Government of Georgia annulated the present Decree (Decree of the State Council of the Republic of Georgia 2000:77-78). The Georgian side was making all efforts to settle the worsened situation and the superior officials of the Central Government were constantly visiting Abkhazia. It was the period when a situation on the Abkhazian segment of the Georgian Railway was complicated acutely, mainly the road was constantly robbed that created a danger for supplies of Georgia, as well as of neighboring republics, mainly Armenia (and tomorrow the war was started 1998:4). All the above-mentioned was supplemented with kidnapping of representatives of the Central Government in the Western Georgia (Nadareishvili 1996:52).

On the date of the 10th of August, 1992, the Presidium of the State Council of the Republic of Georgia adopted a special decree about protection of the railway (the Decree of the State Council of the Republic of Georgia 2002:79). On the 14th of August, 1992, Georgian armed forces entered into the region of Abkhazia and they were obliged to protect the railway that was agreed with the Abkhazian side. However, during their rotation, the forces were met with fire which was resulted in getting of the first victims (Jojua, 2009:158). Actually, this date was recognized as the date of starting of the War in Abkhazia, which was going on till the 27th of September, 1993 and had murdered thousands of Georgians, more than 200 000 people had been internally displaced.

The Georgian side was searching for different ways of peaceful regulation of the conflict, including involving of the Russian Federation into negotiations. The Government of Georgia had addressed to Moscow with a peaceful initiative. On the 3rd of September, 1992, Georgian and Abkhazian sides concluded a treaty, in which one of the parties was also represented by the Russian Federation (Moscow Meeting’s Summarizing Document 2002: 81). Despite of this, it is noteworthy, that the Russian side had done nothing for implementation of the treaty, and, in fact, with this it enhanced strengthening of separatists: “Without any exaggeration we may say, that the Russian side once again revealed its traditional diplomatic perfidy and had done nothing for fulfillment of the “summarized document”. Moreover, being instigated by Moscow, V. Ardzinba, almost immediately, started revision of the Treaty dated by the 3rd of September” (Papaskiri 2007: 380), where the final result was the attack committed against Gagra in the beginning of October of the same year and massacre of Georgians having an image of genocide and ethnic purification. In the battle carried

for Gagra, as well as during the whole war, Abkhazians were supported by the North-Caucasian hired soldiers and Russian Forced Arms. Separatists managed to cross the Russian-Georgian border line and, accordingly, they, in fact without any obstacles had an access to the Russian side by land route. The Gagra's tragedy was beginning of the Georgian's genocide and ethnic purification during the Abkhazian War (Papaskiri 2007: 38). The facts of ethnic purification and genocide in relation to Georgians in Gagra and, generally in Abkhazia was condemned by the International Community and it was reflected in the Decree, one of them is the OSCE Document adopted in Budapest. On top of all, the genocide against Georgians was registered in the OSCE and UN's relevant documents (OSCE-Summit of Heads of State or Government 1996: 3, Aleksidze 2008: 33-46). Resolution of the UN Human Rights Commission and Security Council dated by the 4th of March and 25th of March of 1994 (Resolution 906 of the UN Security Council), as well as in the resolutions of 1995 and 24th of March (Resolution of the UN Security Council 993).

Delivery of the objective information about the processes developed in Abkhazia to the world community for the Georgian side represented a serious problem against the background when the separatistic and Russian media channels had been prepared in advance. They actively were spreading false information about the circumstances existing in the region. (Newest History Central Archive, fund 767, vol.1, case. 111, page. 15-17). According to the Russian author Svetlana Chernovaia: "They were looking for their "supporters" (represented relevantly informed, and warned allies) in the Union ("Commonwealth of Independent States") and foreign centers preliminary. . . Upon reaching of the "relevant peak hour" and starting of the slaughter, "for assisting to the Abkhazian side", "supporters", international observers, TV commentators, "specialists" of the scientific institutes, "Peace Protection Center" and others who had been already trained for this role would start their activity (braces and other precisions belong to authors – G.B.) (Chernovaia 1994:125).

UNPO's organization: targets, structure, members

"UNPO" (Unpresented Nations & Peoples Organization) was founded in the end of the 80s of the XX century. On the first stage the founders, among which were the leader of the Estonian Congress, persecuted by the Communistic regime, sinologist Linart Mall (Jurgenson 2022: 27-37), a representative of the Uighur People Erkin Alptekin and Lodi Gyari from Tibet, and the organization was chaired by the Netherland's Professor in Jurisprudence Michael Walt van Praag, who also acted as the advisor of the Dalai-Lama XIV (<https://unpo.org/about>).

The organization was officially founded in February, 1991, in the Hague Peace Palace. One of the founders was the Republic of Georgia as well

(<https://unpo.org/section/2>), which had a status of a member of the organization in the period since the 11th of February, 1991 – till the 31st of July, 1992, unless Georgia became a member of the UN Organization (Doghonadze 2002:45; Resolution of the UN Organization 763), becoming a member of which is a principal reason for termination of the status of the member of the UNPO for the subject¹. However, during a definite period of time, Georgia was preserving a status of the "supporting member". Here, we would like to note that, on the 24th of March of the same year Georgia became a member of the OSCE (Saralidze 2009:150).

This organization is aimed at assisting to the nations and states which had not been recognized by other states and are not represented in the UN. Accordingly, participation of such subjects in international processes are minimal. The targets also include the issues such as protection of cultural rights, religious rights, right of self-determination, individual human rights, right of heritage (on the territory of any state – G.B.), environmental issues as well, which have an impact on routine life and existing state of these nations (<https://unpo.org/about>).

Targets and tasks of the Organization had been mitigated on the second General Assembly held in August of 1992. A part of the Organization's activity represents preventive actions which must be carried in the regions where there is a constant danger for arising of a conflict between different nations. With the account of the fact that the Organization has poor financial resources, sending of monitoring missions in the problematic regions and, based on the request of the Organization's members, as well as appeals of other states and their work is short-termed. Members of the Mission pay a particular attention on the factors which may cause origination of violence and conflict.

The Georgian National-Democratic Party was collaborating with the stated organization. As for Abkhazia, it became a member of the stated organization in January, 1992 and the so called "Ministry of Foreign Affairs" cooperates with it. (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach, Mall, Praag, Hille 1992:21). A brochure is published on the site of this Organization giving information about a member of this Organization, - Abkhazia (Member Profile of Abkhazia 2012: <https://unpo.org/members/7854>).

Monitoring missions of the stated organization had visited Georgia three times. The first visit was made in July, 1992, based on a request of the Chairman of the Superior Council of the Republic of Abkhazia, Vladislav Ardzinba, chaired by the General Secretary of the same Organization Van Walt van Praag, and in November, the Monitoring Commission arrived in the conflicting territory.

We have two explanatory reports: one is generally about the Mission held in November, 1992, reviewing visits made in July and November (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach, Mall, Praag, Hille, 1992:). The stated report, sometimes later, was published without additional documents in the Edition "Central Asian Survey"

¹ Note: In the process of the survey we contacted the stated organization and requested additional materials on the issues of involving in the Abkhazian war and membership of Geor-

gia in the organization, but he did not obtain additional references except for the official information placed on the website.

(Overeem 1995: 127-154), and the second of the Mission held in 1993 which became a summarized and final document (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach, Mall, Praag, Hille 1993; Overeem 1993:325-345).

In November of 1992 they met the conflicting parties and prepared relevant reports, which one-sidedly and in fact, accuse the Georgian side in the stated conflict. We got acquainted with both conclusions – the first is the report of the UNPO's mission in Abkhazia, Georgia and Northern Caucasus" and the second visit was held in November of 1992 with the "Report of the UNPO's Human Rights Coordination Mission in Abkhazia and Georgia". The stated document summarizes results of the first visit, as well as currency of the war and the processes developed upon the end of the war.

Leader of the Abkhazian separatists Vladislav Ardzinba was accusing the UN Organization and other international organizations in partiality towards Georgia and noted that "in that difficult time when in terms of the informational isolation, spreading of the genuine information about the processes carried in Abkhazia was especially important . . . I addressed to the General Secretary of the UNPO" (Ardzinba 2018: 262).

In the letter dated by the 15th of May, 1992 Vladislav Ardzinba accuses the Georgian side in discriminative politics towards Abkhazia and worsening of the situation.

"During the last years, political management of the Republic of Georgia carries discriminative politics towards the Abkhazian people, striving for independence and facing violent resistance from the Georgian leaders. They carry Anti-Abkhazian hysterics and express accusation in relation to leaders of the Republic of Abkhazia and its Parliament. In addition to it, there is an attempt of a paralleled management and creation of executive authorities in the Republic (probably he considers the National Unity Council – G.B.). Armed divisions are formed (he considered the Sokhumi Mechanized Battalion – G.B.) and they openly declare that they wish to change the Abkhazian Governance. The Superior Council of Abkhazia addresses to you for receiving of urgent measures to avoid using of force against the Abkhazians by the Republic of Georgia and asks you to be a mediator in the process of settlement of the Georgian-Abkhazian conflict in a peaceful way" (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach . . . 1992:30).

Upon the stated appeal, in the beginning of July of 1992 Sokhumi was visited by the General Secretary of the UNPO Michael van Walt van Praag who conducted meetings with the Chairman of the Superior Council of Abkhazia Vladislav Ardzinba, as well as with Abkhazian and Georgian members of the Superior Council and local population (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach . . . 1992:31).

After the visit, on the 14th of July, he sent to the Head of the State Council of Georgia Eduard Shevardnadze and to the leader of the Autonomous Republic of Abkhazia letters in which he summarized results of the visit in Abkhazia, the existing state and considered ways of settlement of the conflict. Contents of these letters were similar. Praag reviews the existing situation and remarks that proceeding from the fact that the relation between the Central Government of Georgian and

the Government of Abkhazia is at a minimal level, all this may cause: "deepening of the conflict which will be followed with surplus complication of the state and as a result of it we will receive a kind of conflict such as the conflict in the Southern Ossetia" (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach . . . 1992:31). In the same letter he reviews a role of each subject in the UNPO, a role of Georgia as of the founding member and that the Georgian National-Democratic Party was collaborating with it. Besides, it notes: "The reason of entering into the organization as a member is that it has contradictions with Georgia or Georgians. In contrary, Georgians solely acquainted and represented, recommended to Abkhazia membership in the UNPO" (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach . . . 1992:32). The author cites that while being in Abkhazia he met, on the first hand, Abkhazian, Russian and Armenian MPs of the Superior Council, and, on another hand "Georgians, who had left a building of the Superior Council and conducted sessions separately. They, differently from you (he addresses to Vladislav Ardzinba – G.B.) have absolutely different positions and, it seems to be, they behave according to the attitudes of the Tbilisi Government" (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach . . . 1993:32). After acquainting and summarizing of positions of all sides he concludes that "all agrees that if the problem is not resolved and a relevant decisions is not made military conflict will start" (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach . . . 1992:33). Here, we would like to remark, that both sides represent generally historical arguments, and based on his assessment, "historical arguments should not be applied while resolving of principal issues despite of the extent of their rationality" (Ennals Farrar, Scholtbach . . . 1993:33). Praag recommends to the Central Government, as well as the Government of Abkhazia to share responsibility in the fields of governance, economics and culture. Besides, he stated, that the worsened situation of Georgia, against the background of other conflicts existing in the Caucasus, faces much more challenges and "I am also sure that if military forces will participate in the struggle for satisfaction of mutual pretensions it will be difficult to find out an outcome and the situation will be changed dramatically" (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach . . . 1992:3). For reaching of the agreement between the parties on resolving of the conflict Praag suggested to carry meetings and discussions in Hague or any other city.

On the 14th of August of 1992 the Government of Georgia sent its troops to the Abkhazian Region. The Chairman of the "Democratic Party of Abkhazia" Guram Gumba, accompanied by two representatives of the Republic of Chechnya departed to Europe, he carried meetings in Geneva and Netherlands and requested sending of special missions for acquainting with the circumstances developed in Abkhazia. On the 11th of September of the same year Vladislav Ardzinba sent a fax to the General Secretary of the UN Organization and the head of the UNPO and also requested sending of the monitoring missions to Abkhazia (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach . . . 1992:35). In the letter sent to the General Secretary of the UN Organization Butros Butros Gali he, surely, accuses the Georgian side in the conflict

and states that “the Georgian side has not made any effort to reject that the main target of this military intervention had been liquidation of the national movement of Abkhazia and cancellation of legitimate authorities of the government and implementation of a kind of regime which would be adoptable for Georgia”. (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach . . . 1992:40). Moreover, he blames the Georgian side in breaching of the peace treaty dated by the 3rd of September, 1992 and genocide of Abkhazians: “Unfortunately, the Georgian side did not fulfill the agreement and the bloodshed is going on. Strict occupational regime was strengthened in Georgia by the Georgian forces. Robbery, murder, raving, and other crimes happen too often. Destroying of cultural monuments and villages received a face of genocide. We address to you with a request to draw attention from the world community on the tragical circumstances existing in our Republic and ask you to make all efforts for suspending of this bloodshed on the Abkhazian land and to investigate the above-mentioned facts” (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach . . . 1992:40). On top of all, it is noteworthy that on the 16th of September, the UN organization’s mission, by a special flight, arrived from Tbilisi and its visit was agreed between Eduard Shevardnadze and Butros Butros-Gali via telephone wire. The mission was aimed at “investigating of the situation developed in the Autonomous Republic and to support settlement of the conflict.

Mission of the UNPO’s in Abkhazia in November of 1992

The next UNPO’s mission arrived in Abkhazia in the period since the 31st of October, 1991 – till the 8th of November. The mission consisted of the member of the British Parliament, a member of the Secret Council of Her Majesty, the former Minister of Health Protection, Lord David Ennals from the Labor Party, Margarethe Farrar, Special Assistant of the American Congressman Tom Lantos, the Vice-President of the Subcommittee of the European and Middle East’s Foreign Affairs, co-Chairman of the Group of Human Rights Protection Group of the Congress; Elvaro Sholtbach, a representative of the apparatus of the Foreign Relations Commission of the Parliament of Netherlands and a member of the Labor Fraction in the Parliament; professor Linart Mall from Estonia, Doctor of the Tartu University, the Vice-Chairman of the Estonian Independence Party and the Vice-President of the UNPO Assembly and Director of the Tartu Branch of the same organization and, finally, the above-mentioned UNPO’s General Secretary and the lawyer Michael van Walt van Praag (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbuch . . . 1992:6).

In scopes of the Mission they met the separatists’ leader Vladislav Ardzinba, Eduard Shevardnadze, the Refugee President of Georgia Zviad Gamsakhurdia and the President of Chechnya Johar Dudaev, as well as officials from Gudauta, Gagra, Sokhumi and Tbilisi (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach...1992:6).

Prior to discussing of definite meetings and steps carried by the Mission, we would like to note that the conclusion prepared by them was characterized with a particular impartiality and anti-Georgian character and in the processes developed in Abkhazia, in the periods

during and prior to the war the Georgian side is accused. For instance, we can read the following abstract in the summarized document:

“The delegation collected significant evidences of the constant cruelty of Georgians towards Abkhazian and other non-Georgian nations that, in the opinion of the Delegation, cannot be recognized only as a disciplinary deficiency in the armed forces. Georgian troops and supporters committed mass robbery and dismantling of Abkhazians’ houses and their cultural organizations. The delegation interviewed peaceful population, including pregnant women and children, who became victims of torturing, beating and murdering from the side of the Georgian soldiers about the cruelty committed by them. These accusations were confirmed by the Georgian official bodies. The Delegation revealed evidences of destroying by Abkhazians in Gagra, where they burnt too many houses in October, after capturing of the city. However, there is no any evidence of mass murder committed by them which was covered by the Georgian media. Such accusation from the Georgian side is a propaganda” (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach . . . 1992:23-24).

This delegation’s report, generally, repeats the Vladislav Ardzinba’s accusations in relation to the international community that “the series of investigations carried by the investigation groups of the UN and OSCE was not sufficient and more attention should be paid to Abkhazia”. (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach . . . 1992:23).

About the facts of breaching of human rights and destroying of cultural inheritance:

The present report is characterized with the anti-Georgian moods. For instance, while reviewing of the historical past of Abkhazia we do not meet an indication that it is an historical region of Georgia. In fact, till the year of 1931 it is discussed as an independent subject, which, voluntarily, joined to the Russian Empire, on the first stage, and then to the Soviet Russia. “And, in 1931, as a result of the Stalin’s caprice, it lost a definite independence and was joined to Georgia with the autonomous status and from this date, oppressing of Abkhazians was started” (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach . . . 1993:331). Georgians are being accused in starting of the war as well. Partiality of reports is caused by the fact that actually there are no vivid Georgian’s positions and arguments. One of the examples of the particular severity committed against Abkhazians are testimonies of Abkhazian physicians, and Georgian physicians had not been interviewed.

Besides, during consideration of the military actions in Gagra, in fact only contradictory positions of the Georgian side were duly expressed. For instance, the author states that “Severe actions committed by Georgian soldiers were caused not only by their “uncontrolled actions”, but were stimulated by the Government of Georgia. They entered into the Abkhazians and non-Georgian houses, burnt, robbed them, raved and murdered citizens and it was confirmed that they had special lists and addressed of victims”. (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach... 1993:338) and all this was happening against the background of several houses burnt by Abkhazians.

According to the document, they had met representatives of the Abkhazian intelligence (names and surnames are not indicated – G.B.) and they accused the Georgian side in intentional damaging of the Abkhazian University, as well as the intentional destroying of the Abkhazian Press and Publishing Houses, schools, institutes, museum, National Archive of Abkhazia (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach ...1993:340).

In the first UNPO's report only one abstract is devoted to the war crimes committed by Abkhazians:

“The delegation determined that Abkhazian and their ally forces expressed severity to the Georgian population, they violated human rights. However, these actions did not carry systematic characters and did not reach the scales of severity revealed from the Georgian side. On top of all, the Abkhazian side makes active steps for investigation of facts of breaching of human rights and punishing of offenders. According to the Georgian army prisoners they were cared well by the Government of Abkhazia. They had been in good conditions and administered a relevant ration of food and they have good relations with Abkhazian soldiers” (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach... 1993-340).

And the second (final) report also has one abstract about crimes of the Abkhazian side:

“On the territory controlled by the Abkhazian Government (e.g. separatistic government – G.B) during the war there had been evidences of Anti-Georgian violence, including punishment with death without the court, burning and robbery of houses and property... especially in October, 1992, after capturing of Gagra by Abkhazian troops. On the final stages when the Abkhazian forces, supported with the North-Caucasian military groups, returned Sokhumi and the remained territory of Abkhazia until the river Enguri, there is evidence of serious breaches. They violated human rights and International Humanitarian Law and upon entering Sokhumi killed a lot of people. However, majority of Georgian had already left the territory of Abkhazia” (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach...1992:13).

The stated is confirmed based on the information shared by one of the ideologists of separatists and politician having Anti-Georgian moods Iuri Voronov, according to which in the period since August, 1992 – till September, 1993, the Government of Abkhazia was controlling a part of the territory, and the headquarter of the government was dislocated in Gutauta. Generally, police did not exist and its functions were fulfilled by the Abkhazian army. The Military Tribunals overtook functions of civil courts. The law did not recognize difference between Georgian and Abkhazian citizens. The Georgian law being applied in Abkhazia did not stipulate provisions of punishing with death. During the war, the Government of Abkhazia initiated punishment with death. Besides, according to Iuri Voronov, during the war the Abkhazian Court had not issued any death verdict and had not executed it (Ennals Farrar, Scholtbach ...1992:329).

The summarized document of the UNPO's first mission represents the following recommendations focused on conflict regulation: it is necessary, as soon as possible, to create and to approve a new initiative which

will provide termination of fire in Abkhazia. This initiative may be implemented on the active mediation of the third party or parties being reliable for both countries. Approval of termination of fire should be followed by serious negotiations on withdrawal of Georgian forces and North-Caucasian allies from Abkhazia; besides, we need strengthening of the activities focused on restoration of belief and determination of the future status of Abkhazia. Any treaty on the future status of Abkhazia and relations with Georgia should have efficient and long-termed guarantees for its implementation (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach... 1993:24).

The UNPO's third mission in Georgia

On the date of the 27th of September, 1993 (the date of the Fall of Sokhumi) too many Georgians were killed, and about 250 000 people became refugees. The UNPO decided to send a new mission to Georgia which would get acquainted with the situation on-site (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach... 1993:4). The mission was working since the 29th of November, 1993 – till the 10th of December, 1993. Participants of the mission: Mikhael van Walt van Praag – UNPO's General Secretary, Pauline Overeem – UNPO's representative, Menelaos Celios – Assistant to the General Secretary of the UN Organization. The above-mentioned person was represented the organization “The International Federation for the Protection of the Rights of Ethnic, Religious, Linguistic and Other Minorities”. The stated mission was also represented by a representative of the UN Organization Geneva Office Hrair Balian, who also represented two international organizations “Human Rights Advocates Resolution (HRA) and COVCAS Center for Law and Conflict Resolution and a representative of the Pax Christi Netherlands Egbert Veselink.

The Mission combined the following routes: Moscow, Gagra, Gutauta, Sokhumi, Ochamchire, Tkvarcheli, Labra, Konstantinovka, Adzvizhba and Tbilisi.

The Georgian side was accusing Abkhazian separatists and their allies in committing of the “ethnic purification”. According to the above-mentioned mission's report: “Reliable evidences of committing of the politics of ethnic purification had not been detected”. (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach... 1993:3).

That time the UN Organization, OSCE and other international organizations were recognizing “ethnic purification” of Georgians in Abkhazia. For instance, the Resolution of the UN Organization dated by the 19th of October, 1993 stated that the “Organization was deeply excited due to humans' torture, ethnic purification, serious breaches of the International Humanitarian and Other laws caused by the regional conflict” (Resolution 876 (1993): 2-3). The UN Organization adopted and shared the report of a Constant Representative of Georgia Petre Chkheidze in the Security Council regarding the stated issue (Georgia State Committee for Investigation 1994:18).

The same issue had been covered by the OSCE's Decree of the Budapest Conference, dated by the 2-3 December of 1994, according to which “they expressed disturbance due to “ethnic purification” and mass displacing of population represented majorly by Georgians.

They had been displaced from their own places of residence and many peaceful citizens had been killed. (CSCE-Budapest Document, 1994:3).

“Ethnical purification” of Georgians in Abkhazia had been condemned in the declaration of the OSCE’s Lisbon Summit of the 3rd of December, 1996: “We (member-states of the OSCE – G.B.) condemn “ethnical purification” in Abkhazia which was expressed main CSCEy by mass murdering of Georgian population and their forced displacement” (Fifth OSCE Summit... 1996:8).

Army prisoners and refugees

Military actions are usually followed by imprisonment of soldiers who are protected by the Geneva Special Convention (Geneva 1949: 2008). In fact, from the first day of military actions in Abkhazia in 1992-1993s, conflicting sides were imprisoning soldiers of the opposite side. The army prisoners were constantly being changed (Karkarashvili 2025: 291-292; Sanaia 1992:3).

In the final report of the Monitoring Mission of the UNPO, a separate extract is devoted to the issue of the army prisoners full of accusation to the Georgian side an representing generally interest of the Abkhazian side. For example, according to the report Georgians killed Abkhazian army prisoners and “representatives of the Government of Georgia asked money from the deceased people’s relative in place of delivery of their corps” (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach... 1993:13). One of the examples of irrelevant treatment with Abkhazians by the Georgian side is a reference that “in March of 1993 during changing of army prisoners Georgians killed 20 Abkhazian army prisoners that is proved by the conclusion prepared by Abkhazians physicians” (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach... 1993:13). Here, it is noted that both sides often imprisoned peaceful citizens to replace them with the army prisoners.

During the military actions carried in Abkhazia and after their ending hundreds of thousands of citizens became refugees, including 250 000 Ethnical Georgians. The UNPO’s report covers the issue of refugees rather peripherally and carries generally statistical character. For instance, they named as a reason of leaving of the Region by the Greek and Israeli population their oppression by the Georgian army and acute economic and criminal situation created after the war (Ennals, Farrar, Scholtbach...1993:16).

To illustrate abruptly negative attitude to the Georgian side we would like to cite the examples connected with the participants of the above-mentioned mission UNPO Linart Malls and David Ennals).

The last meeting of the Monitoring Mission was carried in the capital of Chechnya – Grozny. It was the time when the North Ossetians and Ingushetians had a conflict due to the Prigorodny District and the leader of Chechnya Jokhar Dudaev was trying to settle the conflict. It is noteworthy, that invitation of the UNPO to Abkhazia was initiated by the Chechnya’s leader who had friendly relations with one of the members of the Mission Estonian Linart Mall “since the period when Jokhar Dudaev was serving as the Commander of the Division of Strategic Bombers in Tartu” (Jurgenson 2022:33). Linart Mall was living in the same city and was teaching students in the University. He had

founded the UNPO’s Coordination Office in Tartu which was studying ethnical conflicts existing on the territory of the Western Europe and on the territory of the form USSR. According to the Estonian researcher Aivan Jurgenson Linart Mall had good relations with the leaders of Chechnya and Abkhazia.

As for their attitude to Eduard Shevardnadze, it was abruptly negative, that, probably, had an impact on their conclusion: “The Georgian leader Eduard Shevardnadze was mentioned with uncovered hate, that probably hindered to the UNPO’s mission to be objective. Besides, in one of the interviews, Mall recalls Shevardnadze as a white fox (Jurgenson 2022:3), and in his interview with the Estonian Newspaper “Postiman” he stated that he “had not doubt in defeating of Shevardnadze in the war that would be resulted in releasing of the Caucasus” (Jurgenson 2022:28). The researcher Ayvar Jurgenson explains a negative attitude of Linart Mall towards Eduard Shevardnadze due to his past as, for the Mall, was associated with the communistic regime combatted by himself.

It is noteworthy that Linart Mall, in August, 1992, visited Chechnya where he, on top of detecting of the conflict between the Northern Ossetians and Ingushetians, was working over the newly started Georgian-Abkhazian conflict. Johar Dudaev tried to provide “mediation for the meeting of Shevardnadze and Mall, but Shevardnadze neglected the Dudaev’s attempt for mediation and waived the meeting with Mall as there had been any guarantee in case of flying to Georgia by helicopter” (Jurgenson 2022:29).

And, later in autumn, in cooperation with the UNPO’s delegation, the Vice-President of Chechnya Zelimkhan Yandarbiev visited Georgia and organized a meeting with the Georgian side. The UNPO’s Delegation, together with representatives of the Government of Chechnya was also met by the refugee President Zviad Gamsakhurdia (Jurgenson 2022:5).

According to the same researcher Linart Mall had friendly relations with the leader of the Abkhazian separatists Vladislav Ardzinba (Jurgenson 2022:33). They got acquainted in Moscow, in the Institute of Eastern Disciplines of the Academy of Sciences of the USSR, where Mall was studying eastern religions, mainly budism and Ardzinba was investigating the Khati’s culture for his dissertation.

Linart Mall actively supported Abkhazia in Estonia, as well as on the international forum. And later he called the Government of Estonia to recognize independence of Abkhazia, but the Parliament of Estonia did not discuss this initiative (Jurgenson 2022:31-32). After his death, his daughter, Maia Mall was appearing with the same messages supporting Abkhazia.

Besides, it is important for us to consider several facts connected with the Lord David Ennals. On the 9th of November, 1992, on the day next to the date of ending of the UNPO’s Mission in Georgia, in the British Magazine “Newcastle Journal” David Ennals gave an interview according to which a publication titled “According to the former Minister Georgian troops are guilty in severity” was published (Georgian troops guilty 1992:10), where he strictly criticizes the Georgian side. In the article, the Lord Ennals, who returned

to the Separatistic Region of Georgia from the trip lasting for one week, together with other foreign researchers, declared, that he was absolutely sure in the evidences of the local population that the Georgian troops committed murders, tortures, robbery and destroying of their property". According to the same publication, Georgian soldiers "are hunting on the Abkhazian houses in the conflict zone, beating their owners and many of them had been kidnapped for the purpose of torturing and killing" (Georgian troops guilty 1992:10). The Lord's David Ennal's position regarding the crimes committed by Abkhazians, in the stated article, is represented only with one phrase stating that as a response on the actions of Georgians "Abkhazians, in their turn, had burnt Georgian houses, especially on the shore of the Black Sea" (Georgian troops guilty 1992:10). He considers the prospect of settlement of the conflict very pessimistically. He sees, as one of the outcomes only a desire of both parties to involve the third party in negotiations (Georgian troops guilty 1992:10).

In the same month the Minister of Foreign Affairs of Georgia Aleksandre Chikvaidze, with his delegation, had an official visit to the Great Britain (Georgian Delegation 1992:1). This visit for the country being in terms of the war and economic crisis was particularly significant. That time the Parties concluded four agreements on cooperation in different fields: education, science and culture, investments protection and stimulation agreement about free displacement which is connected with diplomats and agreement of the Ministries of Foreign Affairs on cooperation and consultations (presentation in Chatham House 1992:3; Britain and Georgian agree 1992:12). The visit included presentation of the Minister of Foreign Affairs of Georgia in the Institute of International Affairs of Britain" (Chatham House).

Appearing of the Georgian diplomat in the "Chatham House" had been protested by tens of persons. Aleksandre Chikvaidze states, that "within the hall, as well as outside oppositionally-affected persons were placed as well. Where I say outside, I mean a piquet consisting of 20-30 citizens who rather noisily expressed their protest in relation to the politics of the Government of Georgian in Abkhazia" (Public Speech in the Chatham House 1992:3).

According to the Minister of Foreign Affairs of Georgia, the protestants had vividly expressed "eastern appearance" and behaviour. With the account of the above-mentioned, he considered that they might take a part in the protest initiated by definite people. Moreover, two persons having negative attitude to the Georgian side – Lord David Ennals and the British Abkhasologist Bryan George Hiut had been in the hall. The stated persons in the Newspaper "The Times", issued on the 21st of November, 1992, published a letter "Georgia applies the force", where he recommended to the British Government not to receive Georgian diplomats, not to assist to Georgia, as, in their opinion, the Government of Georgia applied force against Abkhazians and was struggling against them (Georgia's use force 1992:12).

Aleksandre Chikvaidze tried to defuse the situation with humor and noted that "I am very fond of classical music and music in general, I also play the piano

myself, and although the noise coming from the street sounds more like cacophony than classical music, never mind, I will speak accompanied by it" (Speech at Chatham House 1992:30). During his speech, Aleksandre Chikvaidze touched upon the ongoing processes in Abkhazia, and spoke about the particular violence committed against the Georgian population by Abkhazians and their allies there, which had the character of genocide. As Brian George Hewitt writes, David Ennals asked the Georgian diplomat several sharp questions. Lord Ennals told Aleksandre Chikvaidze that he had been in Gagra just two weeks prior and had evidence of violence perpetrated by Georgians against Abkhazians. Aleksandre Chikvaidze replied that "due to the brutal actions of North Caucasians and Abkhazians, virtually every Georgian house from the Russian border to Sukhumi was burned down" (Speech at Chatham House 1992:3), to which Ennals replied that he had personally spoken to the Georgians living there and they remained in their homes. Mark Almond joined the discussion, who had observed the legislative body elections held on October 16, and the conversation shifted to other issues.

After the defeat of the Georgian side in Abkhazia, which was followed by the genocide and ethnic purification of Georgians, the expulsion of hundreds of thousands of citizens was also added. The mentioned organization has not made any statement regarding the genocide and violence. The Chairman of the Committee on Human Rights and Inter-Ethnic Relations, Aleksandre Kavasadze, published a letter addressed to the head of UNPO in the newspaper "Republic of Georgia" (Unsubmitted to the UN 1993:1). Aleksandre Kavasadze directly writes that the Abkhazian separatists, supported by the mentioned organization and personally by Praag, "whom you represent on the international arena, with the moral and military assistance of Russian reactionaries - former Vice-President Ruskoi and former Parliament Speaker Khasbulatov, occupied a divided territory of Georgia" (Unsubmitted to the UN 1993:1). It is also noted that ethnic purification of Georgians and violations of the Geneva Convention are taking place in the occupied territory of Abkhazia, the Georgian population was forced to leave their homes, and all this has been documented by authoritative international organizations such as the UN, OSCE, etc. Considering all this, he calls on Praag to personally come to "see with your own eyes the anti-human nature of the regime you support" (Unsubmitted to the UN 1993:1). Otherwise, it is noted, the impression will be created that UNPO supports and justifies not only separatism and the violation of internationally recognized borders, but also ethnic cleansing (Unsubmitted to the UN 1993:1).

Conclusion

The Abkhazian War represents one of the most difficult and pivotal periods in Georgia's newest history, claiming the lives of thousands of our country's citizens and turning them into displaced persons. The state suffered immense material damage and, in fact, lost control over the region. Various structures of the Russian Federation actively worked in different directions to portray the Georgian side as guilty in the conflict before the international community. The genocide and ethnic purification of Georgians in Abkhazia have

been recognized by the United Nations, the Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe, and other authoritative structures.

Against this backdrop, the conclusions prepared by the "Unrepresented Nations and Peoples Organization" appear biased and non-objective. British politician David Ennals, who recorded positions against the Georgian side and was a supporter of the Abkhazian side's positions in the Great Britain, also participated in the missions of the aforementioned organization.

In fact, the Georgian side has been portrayed as the instigator of the war and the main culprit. The Georgian government has been declared by them as an oppressor of the Abkhazian people and one desiring their deliberate destruction. The conclusions prepared by them are one-sided and are mainly based on information provided by representatives of the separatist authorities. Information provided as a result of surveying the Georgian population is almost nowhere mentioned or is given little consideration.

The presented thesis represents the first attempt to review the work of the observation mission in Georgia and the conclusions prepared by them.

The conclusions of the mentioned organization are actively cited by researchers being unfriendly towards the Georgian side, including the British Abkhazologist Brian George Hewitt. It is also published as a document confirming the "crimes" of Georgians on the propaganda website of the separatist government of Abkhazia. In the presented thesis, we attempted to identify the subjective and objective aspects of the conclusions prepared by the mentioned organization and explain them accordingly. Also included is an explanation of the subjective and unfriendly attitude of several members of the observation mission towards the Georgian side, which would most likely have a negative impact on the objectivity of the prepared conclusion.

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